

Physico-Chemical Studies of Calcium-Lead Hydroxylapatites*

Part II. Thermography

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Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses of calcium-lead hydroxylapatites reveal that absorbed water on the surface of the crystals is lost within about 100° and thereafter within about 500° water trapped in the crystal interior along with water associated with phosphate anions is lost without formation of a definite hydrate. The kinetics were therefore studied thermogravimetrically and the energy of activation of the main steps of dehydroxylation were calculated by Freeman and Correll method. The E values thus obtained were explained on theoretical ground.

As a part of a series of physico-chemical investigations¹ on calcium-lead hydroxylapatites, the present work is an attempt to study the thermo-chemical behaviour of these compounds. Hence thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses of these systems were undertaken and the activation energy was calculated.

Experimental

The details of preparation and identification of the samples of calcium-lead hydroxylapatite systems were reported earlier². The samples used for the thermogravimetric and differential thermal analyses were acetone-washed and air-dried. The TGA work was carried out using an automatic-recording Stanton thermo-balance under dynamic conditions. A convenient weight of each sample of about 0.25 g powder sieved to 200 mesh (B.S.S.) was taken in a silica crucible of about 15 ml capacity and the heating was adjusted to a temperature rise of about 4°/min.

The heating was done in air at one atmosphere pressure. The DTA runs of each sample were obtained by using chromel-alumel thermocouple and stainless steel block. Ignited alumina was the reference material. Temperature was measured with the help of vernier potentiometer and the differential temperature with a ballistic galvanometer (as deflection of the light spot on the scale). The rate of heating was 12°/min.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of a representative set of calcium-lead hydroxylapatites by the method specially worked out³ and their activation energies at two different temperatures are given in Table 1. The experimental wt. % errors of the determination of concentrations of Ca²⁺, Pb²⁺ and (PO₄)³⁻ when present together as in the case CaHA-PbHA systems were respectively ±0.14%, ±0.08% and 0.00% while the corresponding errors

TABLE I. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM LEAD-HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR ACTIVATION ENERGY

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	g.atom ratio Ca+Pb P	Activation energy K/cal/mole
	Ca	Pb	P			
1	38.39	—	18.61	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	28.3
2	19.10	40.33	12.48	Ca _{7.1} Pb _{2.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	30.1
3	10.89	56.28	10.10	Ca _{5.0} Pb _{5.0} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	32.4
4	5.09	67.57	8.43	Ca _{2.8} Pb _{7.2} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.67	34.7
5	1.45	74.63	7.37	Ca _{0.9} Pb _{9.1} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	36.2
6	—	77.43	6.95	Pb ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	1.68	39.5

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of (PO₄)³⁻ when present either with Ca²⁺ or Pb²⁺ as in the case of CaHA, PbHA was 0.00%. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g atoms of calcium and/or lead the molecular

formulae of the samples were calculated from the results of columns 2-3 and included in Table 1. The atomic ratio of $\frac{\text{Ca}+\text{Pb}}{\text{P}}$ in a mole of each sample was calculated from the analytical data and in each case was found to be approaching the theoretical value of 1.67, which indicates the formation of the apatite lattice⁴ and the accuracy of the analytical procedure adopted for the purpose.

The results of the thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis of a representative set of the samples namely sample nos. 1, 3 and 6 of Table 1 are diagrammatically represented in the Fig. 1 as

curve in between is smooth and has no distinct horizontals, indicating the loss of weight within this range as a continuous function of temperature resulting dehydroxylation. The horizontal at lower temperature induction period of dehydration of crystalline samples and the other at higher temperature beyond 500° indicates complete dehydration. The absence of distinct horizontals between these two temperatures reveals the absence of formation of a definite hydrate⁵ of the hydroxylapatite.

The DTA curve of each sample consisted of mainly one sharp endothermic peak at lower temperature (within about 150°) and a distinct exothermic peak

Fig. 1. Thermochemical behaviour of calcium-lead hydroxylapatites and their solid solutions. (Refer Table 1, samples 1, 3 and 6 respectively).

gravimetric thermocurves and differential thermocurves. The TG curve in each case consisted of two horizontals, one corresponding to the commencement of the loss in weight at about 80° and the other corresponding to the attainment of constancy of weight at higher temperature of about 500°. The

at higher temperature (between 260°-400°). The endothermic peak in the DTA curve is due to removal of the absorbed water on the surface of the crystals and the exothermic peak at about 260°-400° may be due to some internal changes in the crystalline lattice. Because one thing is certain that the exothermic

peak does not correspond to any decomposition of the hydroxylapatite systems, as it is a well established fact that hydroxylapatite systems does not undergo decomposition even when they are heated upto 1450°. Any way the reason for exothermic peak for hydroxylapatite systems is under detailed study. The absence of any change in the unit cell dimension of the heated and unheated apatite systems and the absence of any new lines in the X-ray diffraction patterns further confirms the non-appearance of any new phase during heating⁷. In summary the thermographical studies revealed uniform loss of water during dehydration without the formation of any stable hydrate within about 800°.

The thermogravimetric data have been used to calculate the kinetic parameters (activation energy) by the dehydration of the calcium-lead hydroxylapatites applying the Freeman and Carroll equation⁸.

$$\frac{-E/2.3R\Delta(T^{-1})}{\Delta\log W_r} = -X + \frac{\Delta\log(dw/dt)}{\Delta\log W_r}$$

where E = activation energy, R = general gas constant, T = absolute temperature, X = order of the reaction and $W_r = W_c - W$, where W_c = loss of weight of the completion of the reaction and W = loss of weight at time t . A plot of $\Delta\log(dw/dt)/\Delta\log W_r$ versus $\Delta(T^{-1})/\Delta\log W_r$ gave a straight line with a slope of $\pm E/2.3R$ and an intercept of X for a straight stage irreversible reaction. From the data it is found that the value of X in every case is equal to ~ 1 and the calculated E values are given in the Table 1. It is found from the values that the activation energy of the sample increases with increase in the

lead content of the samples. This is in agreement with the entropy⁹ values of Ca^{2+} and Pb^{2+} ions, the entropy of Pb^{2+} is higher than that of Ca^{2+} , so it is expected that the activation energy values of the samples should increase with the increase in the lead content of the samples.

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